

LUCCIA

User Guide

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Table of content

How does LUCCIA work?	3
Basics	3
Initialisation	Erreur ! Signet non défini.
Processes	4
Interventions	5
User Interface	6
Building scenarios using LUCCIA user interface	6
LUCCIA / PRESENTATION	8
LUCCIA / SCENARIO	8
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / GENERAL	9
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / POPULATION	9
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / CROP	10
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / TREE	11
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / AGROFORESTRY	12
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / INTENSIFICATION	13
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / TREE PLANTATION	13
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / FOREST RESTORATION	14
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION	15
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / PROTECTED AREA	16
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / INTENSIFICATION	16
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / ROAD	17
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / AGROFORESTRY	18
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / PLANTATION	18
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / FOREST RESTORATION	19
LUCCIA / SCENARIO / CONTROL OUTPUT	20
LUCCIA / SIMULATION	20
LUCCIA / INDICATORS	20
LUCCIA / EXTREME EVENTS	22
LUCCIA / PROJECT EVALUATION	23

How does LUCCIA work?

Basics

- In LUCCIA, we model the main activities of rural households and their impacts on natural forests. These activities include cultivating cropland and clearing forest land when more space is required for cultivation,
- Mozambique is divided in 1 km² land units. About 800,000 land units are required.
- Within each land unit, we keep track of many variables that constitute the state of the system. For example, each land unit contain the respective surfaces of land cover types (e.g. cropland, urban, miombo, plantation, water) which add up to 100 ha. Associated with the cropland, we have a number of households and other related information (e.g. number of members, type of household, their cropland, the crops they cultivate a given year, etc.). There is also the number of trees of different types (timber, nut, fruit, and fertilizer).
- The system is initialised in 2017, and each year, different processes occur that changes the state of the system until the end of the simulation period (e.g. 2037).
- By changing the parameters of the processes, different simulation runs can be made that correspond to different scenarios. The result data saved each year for each scenario can be compared and their respective interests assessed.

Initialization

- The initialisation of the system means deciding what is inside each of the 800,000 land units covering Mozambique.
- The respective surfaces of the different land cover types in each land unit is obtained from upscaling the FNDS 2016 Land Use / Land Cover map.
- Putting people and households in the land units must be done considering at the same time: 1) INE 2017 census urban and rural population at posto level, 2) the cropland and urban land surfaces from the FNDS 2016 Land Use / Land Cover map and 3) the household characteristics at province level according to the IAS 2015 survey of about 5800 households in Mozambique.
- We use a household typology with 4 types: HH1 subsistence, HH2 with some cash crop, HH3 with some livestock and HH4 small and emerging farmers. From the IAS survey, we obtain characteristics and statistics per HH type, per province, concerning the number of HH members, the land surface cultivated, in fallow, the main trees in their cropland, the types of crops and their respective area cultivated.
- These characteristics are then used to populate the land units with people, households, trees, and crops.
- Other sources of information are used. The road network, the protected area network, together with the existing cropland area are used to generate an "*attractivity*" map, which gives the probability of other land (grassland, forest) being converted into new cropland. Then, there are crop *suitability maps* and tree suitability maps which are used for deciding whether a certain crop or tree can grow in a given land unit.

Processes

- During a simulation, we start from the initial state (i.e. 2017) and calculate a new state for each time step (i.e. 1 year) until the end of the simulation period (e.g. 2037).
- A new state is obtained from a previous state through the action of several processes related to the activities of the households.
- One of the main processes is *population dynamics*. Population growth is modelled according to INE projections. Population birth and mortality rates are applied at province level with different values for urban and rural populations. New population is then distributed towards districts, then postos and finally to land units.
- This process is closely linked to the *migration* process where population from land unit level can be aggregated (bottom-up) and displaced (top-down) to other administrative levels (posto, district or province). They move to urban areas, other districts in their own province, or to other provinces. The inter-province migration follows the origin-destination matrix of the INE. A parameter controls the proportion of migrating population going to urban areas.
- We model *household dynamics* where households can be upgraded or downgraded in the HH1 to HH4 spectrum according to their income from crop and tree production during several consecutive years. Those that become candidates for migration are HH1 that have undergone recurring adverse conditions.
- **Crop** cultivation is modelled at household level. Each household has a surface area of cropland. For a given year, part of the cropland is cultivated (according to the fallow duration map), and the rest is left as fallow. Each household cultivates between 1 and 5 different crops among a list of 10 crops (9 main crops like maize, feijao, rice, etc. and an unspecified 'other' crop). The crops chosen respect the crop suitability maps. To obtain household crop production, we multiply crop area by yield taken from pre-calculated yield maps. These were generated using a crop model (SARRA-O) run with four crop intensification levels and fed with input meteorological data generated from a GCM for simulated climate scenarios (SSP126 and SSP585). Then crop price projections are used to convert production into income for the households. The table with the four HH types in lines and the four intensification levels in columns is called the *intensification matrix*. Each value of the matrix gives the percentage of HH of a given type to use a given intensification level. Therefore, each line of the matrix adds up to 100%.
- Most rural households have *trees* in their cropland. Four types of trees (nut=caju; fruit=mango; timber=eucalyptus and fertilizer=faidherbia) are modelled. At initialisation only caju and mango are distributed in the land units. The annual production also provide an income to the households. Production are not based on climate scenario, but on known average. Income are calculated according to price projections.
- During migration, part of the households are attracted towards *urban* areas. They contribute to increase existing urban areas within land units, but also those in the surrounding land units through *urban sprawl*.

Interventions

- Other processes are modelled related to *interventions*. Development projects through their interventions influence the activities of the households. Each intervention is defined by a date (i.e. year) when it begins, a duration (i.e. number of years) and project area (i.e. a polygon or an administrative unit).
- The *road building* intervention consists in installing new roads which will change the attractivity of the nearby land units.
- Through *natural resource conservation* measures, such as increasing the protected area network, increasing the protection status of certain areas, or creating new conservation areas, will also reduce the attractivity of these areas for new households.
- There are projects that target households by helping them improve their crop production through *agricultural intensification*, e.g. using, inputs, better crop varieties or overall better technical package. This is modelled by changing the intensification matrix for a given project area e.g. a district. This can be done by increasing the percentage of higher intensification levels for the targeted household types.
- There are six more types of interventions available at national scale, two of each concerning respectively *forestry plantation*, *agroforestry system* and *forest restoration*.
- One type of forestry plantation intervention is the *industrial tree plantation*. In existing DUATs, some local households lose their lands to industrial companies. New pulp or timber plantations are installed and the land cover is changed accordingly.
- In buffer zones around these tree plantations, HH4 households can have *individual tree plantations*. They will reduce some of their cropland and grow trees on them. These trees will provide them an income by selling to the industrial company nearby.
- Another important intervention is to promote agroforestry systems (AFS). In *cash crop AFS*, HH4 households living in areas where the cash crop (e.g. cashew) is possible (i.e. according to the tree suitability map) receive seedlings to be planted in order to increase the number of cash crop trees in their cropland. After some years, the trees grow bigger and the cultivated land is reduced. More cash crop trees mean more production and income for the household.
- *Diverse AFS* promotion consists in targeting all HH types and encouraging them to grow more and diverse trees in their cropland. The gain in fertility of the cropland due to diverse AFS allows reducing the fallow duration to compensate the cropland surface occupied by trees.
- An intervention proposed will target highly degraded forested areas through *active forest restoration*. These highly degraded forest areas are selected within KBA, conservation areas or forest concessions. Attractivity is set to 0 to prevent new households coming in. Grassland, fallow, and cropland are actively restored to become natural forest.
- For moderately degraded forest areas in these KBA, conservation areas or forest concessions, there can be *passive forest restoration*. Attractivity is also set to 0 to prevent new households coming in. Natural regeneration will gradually convert grassland and fallow into forest. Total farm area of the target zones is also reduced.

Table 1: Model structure and processes

Module Name in Luccia code	Involved in	What it does
Init_Module	Initialisation of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • read model parameters • read LULC map and extract LC surfaces per 1 km² land unit
Attractivity_Module	Initialisation of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compute attractivity of each land unit based on raster, vector (polygons, polylines) • Load previously computed attractivity
Suitability_Module	Initialisation of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read crop suitability maps • Generate crop suitability vectors (csv file, tif raster)
Population_Module	Population dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply rural and urban population growth and mortality rates
Migration_Module	Horizontal HH dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage inter- and intra-province HH migrations
Urban_Module	Initialisation of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read urban population at postos level and distribute in land units
	Horizontal HH dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban pop dynamics and urban sprawl
Households_Module	Initialisation of the system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate rural households and place in land units, respecting postos census, IAS HH stats and LULC map
	Land cover change	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate new HH from pop increase and incoming migration, distribute in land units and convert land
Case_studies_Module	Application to case studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define and manage a case study • Set parameters, input data, define processes
Tree_Module	Application to case studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assign trees to HH according to IAS tree stats and tree suitability maps • Calculate tree production each year, and convert into HH income using prices
Crop_Module	Household cropping plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate HH cropping plans that respect crop suitability maps and IAS HH crop stats
	Crop area to crop production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generate crop production each year from yield maps (obtained from crop model running on climate scenarios)
	Crop production to welfare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From HH crop productions, calculate HH income
HHDyn_Module	Vertical and Horizontal HH dynamics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using HH income as welfare index over several years, upgrade or downgrade HH

User Interface

Building scenarios using LUCCIA user interface

- **Luccia** can be used to test the effects of projects against the business-as-usual baseline.
- It comes with a user interface that allows to:
 - Define **Scenarios** for case studies at national or local levels
 - Run **Simulations**
 - Display **Indicators** resulting from simulations
 - Evaluate potential impacts of **Extreme Events**

- Conduct **Project Evaluation**

This user guide explains the different functions that can be used through the interface. The design and analysis of case studies (National and Local) are described in the two accompanying reports.

Figure 1: Luccia software interface

Figure 2: LUCCIA software tree structure

LUCCIA / PRESENTATION

Purpose

- Gives a general overview of the LUCCIA software.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO

Purpose

- Allows:
 - Accessing and modifying existing scenarios.

Usage

- Select existing scenario in the drop-down list

- Save a modified existing scenario using

- Save a copy of the current scenario with a new name using . This is a way to create a new scenario from an existing one, and be able to change the settings of that new scenario later.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / GENERAL PARAMETERS

Purpose

- Allows:
 - Setting Begin and End year of simulation period,
 - Setting the input Land Use Land Cover map of Mozambique

The default Begin and End years are 2017-2037. However, crop yield maps and price tables are provided to run simulations until 2050.

The reference Land Use Land Cover map used is the FNDS 2016 map. For each 1 km² land unit, the respective surface area of the following classes used in LUCCIA (Crop, Grassland, Mangrove, Mecrusse, Miombo, Mopane, Open Water, Other, Peatland, Plantation and Urban) are extracted and saved in separate tif files. Each simulation year, a tif file is created for each land cover type, and contains the changes in land cover compared to the previous year.

Usage

- Select Begin and End simulation year from the drop-down lists

The image shows a user interface with two dropdown menus. The first dropdown is labeled 'Begin year' and has '2017' selected. The second dropdown is labeled 'End year' and has '2037' selected. Both dropdowns have a small downward-pointing arrow on the right side.

- Select Reference Land Use and Land Cover map by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / POPULATION

Purpose

- Allows:
 - Setting Rural areas growth (birth) and loss (mortality) rates
 - Setting Urban areas growth and loss rates
- Allows:
 - Setting Rural and Urban population migration ratios
 - Setting Inter-Province Origin-Destination matrix file

The default parameters reproduce the official population projections of the INE 2017 census. Other population projections (e.g. UN, World Bank) can be achieved by changing the appropriate parameters in the interface. The projections can include a decrease in growth and loss rates that is also parameterized.

For each administrative unit (e.g. posto) there is an increase in population every year. A percentage of the new (urban and rural) population become candidates for migration and are aggregated at province level. Then the origin-destination matrix is used to dispatch these population to other provinces. A parameter is available to set which part of the rural migrants will move to urban areas.

Usage

- Set parameters separately for Urban and Rural populations
- For each of these two (Urban and Rural) populations, use four slide buttons to set:

- Initial growth rate in % per year (e.g. 1% gives 1% more population every year)
- Growth rate change in % per year (e.g. with -0.01% , growth rate decreases by 0.01% every year)
- Initial loss rate in % per year
- Loss rate change in % per year

- Select the origin-destination matrix file by clicking on to open file selection window
- Use the three slide buttons to set the migration ratios:
 - Rural – Urban migration coefficient
 - New Urban population migration ratio
 - New Rural population migration ratio

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / CROP

Purpose

- Allows:
 - Choosing the climate scenario by setting the folder containing the crop yield maps generated using simulated climate data from 2017 to 2050
 - Setting projected crop prices from 2017 to 2050.

Yield maps are available for cassava, cotton, feijao, groundnut, maize, rice, sesame, sorghum, tobacco and other (average of the 9 other crops). For each year during the period 2017-2050, they were generated using a crop model (Sarra-O) driven by input data generated from climate models, with four levels of intensification (corresponding to four levels of technical agricultural packages, ranging from low to good use of fertilizers, mechanisation, and appropriate crop varieties.

The projected crop prices were obtained by extrapolating the current price trends.

Usage

- Select the climate scenario folder containing the crop yield maps by clicking on to open folder selection window.

- Select the crop prices table by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / TREE

Purpose

- Allows setting the projected tree product prices from 2017 to 2050.

Unlike for crops, tree productions have been estimated based on average values, and not based on climate simulations.

Usage

- Select the tree product prices table by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION

Table 2: National interventions

Mitigation Measures	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET REDD+ and CC adaptation scenario
Tree plantation	Industrial plantation	Tree plantation DUAT above 1000 ha (60 polygons)	Increase of tree plantation area. In detriment of cropland, grassland. Two type (timber, pulp) with different tree rotation that calculate income from harvest	Depends on the scenario. Baseline : 2017-2037 Intervention : 2020-2030	1000 ha by year (TP_Industrial_baseline.shp)	25 000 ha by year (TP_Industrial_intervention.shp)
	Individual plantation	Around commercial plantation with a 20 km buffer	Eucalyptus for pulp or pole. Targeted on HH4 only. Reduce the available farm area	From 2017 to 2037	0 Ha	1 000 ha by year (TP_Individual_intervention.shp)
Agroforestry	Cashew AFS	All mozambique, target by province, Tree suitability map	Targeted on HH4 only. Target of seedling, integration of success rate by province	Now, annual increment 2017-2027 (10 years program)	2 million seedlings by year for household with existing cashew trees (AFS_Cashew_baseline.shp)	4 million seedlings by year for household with existing cashew trees (AFS_Cashew_intervention.shp)
	Diverse AFS	All mozambique, target by province, Tree suitability map	All HH type. Diverse AFS surface is taken from fallow area and converted to cropland	From 2017 to 2037	0 Ha	1 500 ha by year (AFS_Divers_intervention.shp)
Forest restoration	Active restoration	10 biggest areas with highly degraded land within KBA, Forest Concessions and Protected Areas	All HH type. Target annual restoration hectares by polygons. Conversion of grassland, fallow and cropland to forest	From 2017 to 2037	0 ha	7 500 ha by year (FR_Active_intervention.shp)
	Passive restoration	10 biggest areas with moderately degraded land within KBA, Forest Concessions and Protected Areas	All HH type. Target annual restoration hectares by polygons. Conversions of grassland, fallow and cropland to forest	From 2017 to 2037	0 ha	7 500 ha by year (FR_Passive_intervention.shp)

Purpose

- Configure a new national intervention scenario by combining and parameterizing several processes:
 - Agroforestry
 - Intensification
 - Tree plantation

- o Forest restoration

Once a new national intervention scenario is created, it can be configured by selecting one or more of predefined processes and parameterizing them.

Usage

- Select each of the processes to be included by clicking on the appropriate tab
- The explanations for configuring each process are given in the following pages. LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / AGROFORESTRY

Mitigation Measures	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET REDD+ and CC adaptation scenario
Agroforestry	Cashew AFS	All mozambique, target by province, Tree suitability map	Targeted on HH4 only, Target of seedling, integration of success rate by province	Now, annual increment 2017-2027 (10 years program)	2 million seedlings by year for household with existing cashew trees (AFS_Cashew_baseline.shp)	4 million seedlings by year for household with existing cashew trees (AFS_Cashew_intervention.shp)
	Diverse AFS	All mozambique, target by province, Tree suitability map	All HH type Diverse AFS surface is taken from fallow area and converted to cropland	From 2017 to 2037	0 Ha	1 500 ha by year (AFS_Divers_intervention.shp)

Purpose

- Allows activating and configuring agroforestry system (AFS) processes within a national intervention scenario:
 - o Cashew AFS
 - o Diverse AFS

The targets of the interventions are set per province directly in the shapefiles. For Cashew AFS, the target is the number of seedlings distributed per year (column NB_SEED) and the success rate of the seedlings (column SUC_RATE). For Diverse AFS, the target is the new surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) in diversification agroforestry per province. The targets in the table above are distributed among the polygons in the shapefile.

Usage

- Activate Cashew AFS and/or Diverse AFS using the switch buttons
- For each AFS intervention, select:

- o Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- o Duration (in years) using slide button.

- o Study area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / INTENSIFICATION

Purpose

- Allows improving crop production for selected postos by increasing crop intensification.

Yield maps with four levels of intensification are available for the main crops in Mozambique between 2017 and 2050. For each household type (HH1, HH2, HH3 and HH4), the households in a posto will adopt different intensification levels. We use four coefficients (the sum of which is equal to 1) that gives the distribution of households with each intensification level. For example, in the figure above, a set of coefficients (0.1, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3) for HH1 means that 10% of the households of type 1 in the given posto will adopt Intensification level 1 (lowest), 10% with Intensification level 2 (low), 50% with Intensification level 3 (average) and 30% with Intensification level 4 (above average). The postos on which the new Intensification levels are applied are read from the shapefile. To generate that shapefile, open the LUCCIA posto shapefile, select the required postos and save them to a new shapefile using "Export/Save selected features as..." in QGIS.

Usage

- Activate the Intensification process using the switch buttons
- Select the:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- Duration (in years) using slide button.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / TREE PLANTATION

Mitigation Measures	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET REDD+ and CC adaptation scenario
Tree plantation	Industrial plantation	Tree plantation DUAT above 1000 ha (60 polygons)	Increase of tree plantation area. In detriment of cropland, grassland. Two type (timber, pulp) with different tree rotation that calculate income from harvest	Depends on the scenario. Baseline : 2017-2037 Intervention : 2020-2030	1000 ha by year (TP_Industrial_baseline.shp)	25 000 ha by year (TP_Industrial_intervention.shp)
	Individual plantation	Around comercial plantation with a 20 km buffer	Eucalyptus for pulp or pole. Targeted on HH4 only. Reduce the available farm area	From 2017 to 2037	0 Ha	1 000 ha by year (TP_Individual_intervention.shp)

Purpose

- Allows activating and configuring Tree plantation processes within a national intervention scenario:
 - Industrial plantation

- o Individual plantation

The targets of the interventions are set per polygons directly in the shapefiles. For Industrial tree plantations, the target is the surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) where new Industrial tree plantations are installed. For Individual tree plantation, the target is the surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) where new Individual tree plantations are installed by HH4 households on their cropland in the vicinity of existing Industrial plantations. The targets in the table above are distributed among the polygons in the shapefile.

Usage

- Activate Industrial plantation and/or Individual plantation processes using the switch

buttons

- For each tree plantation intervention, select:

- o Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- o Duration (in years) using slide button.

- o Study area shapefile by clicking on

to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / NATIONAL INTERVENTION / FOREST RESTORATION

Mitigation Measures	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET REDD+ and CC adaptation scenario
Forest restoration	Active restoration	10 biggest areas with highly degraded land within KBA, Forest Concessions and Protected Areas	All HH type Target annual restoration hectares by polygons Conversion of grassland, fallow and cropland to forest	From 2017 to 2037	0 ha	7 500 ha by year (FR_Active_intervention.shp)
	Passive restoration	10 biggest areas with moderately degraded land within KBA, Forest Concessions and Protected Areas	All HH type Target annual restoration hectares by polygons Conversions of grassland, fallow and cropland to forest	From 2017 to 2037	0 ha	7 500 ha by year (FR_Passive_intervention.shp)

Purpose

- Allows activating and configuring Forest restoration processes within a national intervention scenario:
 - o Active forest restoration
 - o Passive forest restoration

The targets of the interventions are set per polygon directly in the shapefiles. For both Active and Passive Forest restoration, the target is the surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) for which forest restoration measures are applied. The targets in the table above are distributed among the polygons in the shapefile.

Usage

- Activate Active and/or Passive Forest restoration processes using the switch buttons

- For each forest restoration intervention, select:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- Duration (in years) using slide button.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION

Table 3: Local interventions

Interventions	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET PDUT and CC adaptation scenario
Tree plantation	Industrial plantation	4 DUATs (1 from IFLOMA and 3 from Portucel)	Same as national	Baseline : 2017-2037 Intervention : 2020-2030	40 ha by year (PLANT_HA colum) (TP_Industrial_baseline_local.shp)	200 ha by year (PLANT_HA) (TP_Industrial_intervention_local.shp)
	Individual plantation	Buffer zone of existing forest DUAT	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	125 ha by year (PLANT_HA) (TP_individual_intervention_local.shp)
	Commercial agriculture	Spatial delineation for baseline plus selected area for intervention	Same as national	2017-2037	TP_CA_baseline_local.shp	TP_CA_intervention_local.shp
Agroforestry	Coffee AFS	Selected existing coffee area for baesline and PDUT for intervetion	Targeted on HH1 only	2017-2037	6400 seedlings by year (NB_SEED) (AFS_Coffee_baseline_local.shp)	125000 seedlings by year (NB_SEED) (AFS_Coffee_intervention_local.shp)
	Diverse AFS	NA	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	350 ha by year (PLANT_HA) (AFS_diverse_intervention_local.shp)
Forest restoration	Active restoration	PDUT zone	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	600 ha by year (REST_HA) (FR_Active_intervention_local.shp)
	Passive restoration	PDUT zone	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	450 ha by year (REST_HA) (FR_Passive_intervention_local.shp)
Protected area	Improved Management	4 PA (chimanimani core area, buffer zone, Moribane forest reserve) for baseline and 5 PA for the intervention (+ coutada PDUT)	Same as national	2017-2037	Various level of land accessibility (PERMEA) PA_baseline_local.shp	Various level of land accessibility (PERMEA) PA_intervention_local.shp
Roads	Rehabilitation and building	Existing road database for baseline and road PDUT for intervetion	Same as national	2017-2037	Road_baseline_local.shp	Road_intervention_local.shp

Purpose

- Configure a new local intervention scenario by combining and parameterizing several processes:
 - Protected area
 - Intensification
 - Road
 - Agroforestry
 - Plantation
 - Forest restoration

Once a new local intervention scenario is created, it can be configured by selecting one or more of predefined processes and parameterizing them.

Usage

- Select each of the processes to be included by clicking on the appropriate tab.
- The explanations for configuring each process are given in the following pages.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / PROTECTED AREA

Interventions	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET PDUT and CC adaptation scenario
Protected area	Improved Management	4 PA (chimanimani core area, buffer zone, Monibane forest reserve) for baseline and 5 PA for the intervention (+ coutada PDUT)	Same as national	2017-2037	Various level of land accessibility (PERMEA) PA_baseline_local.shp	Various level of land accessibility (PERMEA) PA_intervention_local.shp

Purpose

- Increase the existing Protected Area (PA) network by:
 - Creating new PAs or
 - Restraining accessibility of existing PAs

The new PAs and new status of existing PAs are read in a shapefile. The polygons representing the PAs has a column "PERMEA" which contains a permeability value between 0 (high protection) and 100 (low protection). This value is used to modify the attractivity map used in LUCCIA for deciding where new households are installed. The new attractivity value overwrites the existing attractivity value inside the polygon of the PA.

Usage

- Activate the Protected Area process using the switch buttons
- Select:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- There is no need to specify intervention duration as PAs are assumed to remain protected until the end of the simulation.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / INTENSIFICATION

Purpose

- Allows improving local crop production for selected postos by increasing crop intensification.

Yield maps with four levels of intensification are available for the main crops in Mozambique between 2017 and 2050. For each household type (HH1, HH2, HH3 and HH4), the households in a posto will adopt different intensification levels. We use four coefficients (the sum of which is equal to 1) that gives the distribution of households with each intensification level. For example, in the figure above, a set of coefficients (0.1, 0.1, 0.5, 0.3) for HH1 means that 10% of the households of type 1 in the given posto will adopt Intensification level 1 (lowest), 10% with Intensification level 2

(low), 50% with Intensification level 3 (average) and 30% with Intensification level 4 (above average). The postos on which the new Intensification levels are applied are read from the shapefile. To generate that shapefile, open the LUCCIA posto shapefile, select the required postos and save them to a new shapefile using "Export/Save selected features as..." in QGIS.

Usage

- Activate the Intensification process using the switch buttons
- Select the:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- Duration (in years) using slide button.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / ROAD

Interventions	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET PDUT and CC adaptation scenario
Roads	Rehabilitation and building	Existing road database for baseline and road PDUT for intervention	Same as national	2017-2037	Road_baseline_local.shp	Road_intervention_local.shp

Purpose

- Improve accessibility of study area by installing new roads

The installation of new roads will improve the attractiveness of land units near the new roads. The attractiveness improvement is parameterized using the attractiveness ratio e.g. the attractiveness of a given land unit is multiplied by (1 + attractiveness ratio) weighted by the distance of the land unit to the new road.

Usage

- Activate the New Road process using the switch buttons
- Select the:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- There is no need to specify intervention duration as the roads are assumed to remain until the end of the simulation.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window
- Set the new road attractiveness ratio using the slide button.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / AGROFORESTRY

Interventions	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET PDUT and CC adaptation scenario
Agroforestry	Coffee AFS	Selected existing coffee area for baseline and PDUT for intervention	Targeted on HH1 only	2017-2037	6400 seedlings by year (NB_SEED) (AFS_Coffee_baseline_local.shp)	125000 seedlings by year (NB_SEED) (AFS_Coffee_intervention_local.shp)
	Diverse AFS	NA	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	350 ha by year (PLANT_HA) (AFS_diverse_intervention_local.shp)

Purpose

- Allows activating and configuring agroforestry system (AFS) processes within a local intervention scenario:
 - Coffee AFS
 - Diverse AFS

The targets of the local interventions are set per polygon directly in the shapefiles. For Coffee AFS, the target is the number of seedlings distributed per year (column NB_SEED) and the success rate of the seedlings (column SUC_RATE). For Diverse AFS, the target is the new surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) in diversification agroforestry per polygon. The targets in the table above are distributed among the polygons in the shapefile.

Usage

- Activate Coffee AFS and/or Diverse AFS using the switch buttons
- For each AFS intervention, select:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- Duration (in years) using slide button

- Study area shapefile by clicking on

to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / PLANTATION

Interventions	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET PDUT and CC adaptation scenario
Tree plantation	Industrial plantation	4 DUATs (1 from IFLOMA and 3 from Portucel)	Same as national	Baseline : 2017-2037 Intervention : 2020-2030	40 ha by year (PLANT_HA colum) (TP_Industrial_baseline_local.shp)	200 ha by year (PLANT_HA) (TP_Industrial_intervention_local.shp)
	Individual plantation	Buffer zone of existing forest DUAT	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	125 ha by year (PLANT_HA) (TP_individual_intervention_local.shp)
	Commercial Agriculture	Spatial delineation for baseline plus selected area for intervention	Same as national	2017-2037	TP_CA_baseline_local.shp	TP_CA_intervention_local.shp

Purpose

- Allows activating and configuring plantation processes within a local intervention scenario:
 - Commercial agriculture
 - Industrial plantation
 - Individual plantation

The targets of the interventions are set per polygon directly in the shapefiles. For Industrial tree plantations, the target is the surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) where new Industrial tree plantations are installed. For Individual tree plantation, the target is the surface area (hectares;

column SUR_HA) where new Individual tree plantations are installed by HH4 households on their cropland in the vicinity of existing Industrial plantations. The targets in the table above are distributed among the polygons in the shapefile. For commercial agriculture, the target is the surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) where new commercial agriculture (here litchi and macadamia) is installed.

Usage

- Activate Commercial agriculture, Industrial plantation and/or Individual plantation

processes using the switch buttons

- For each plantation intervention, select:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- Duration (in years) using slide button.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on

to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / LOCAL INTERVENTION / FOREST RESTORATION

Interventions	Action	Where	What (see details in notes)	When	TARGET Scenario Business-as-Usual	TARGET PDUT and CC adaptation scenario
Forest restoration	Active restoration	PDUT zone	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	600 ha by year (REST_HA) (FR_Active_intervention_local.shp)
	Passive restoration	PDUT zone	Same as national	2017-2037	0 ha	450 ha by year (REST_HA) (FR_Passive_intervention_local.shp)

Purpose

- Allows activating and configuring Forest restoration processes within a local intervention scenario:
 - Active forest restoration
 - Passive forest restoration

The targets of the interventions are set per polygon directly in the shapefiles. For both Active and Passive Forest restoration, the target is the surface area (hectares; column SUR_HA) for which forest restoration measures are applied. The targets in the table above are distributed among the polygons in the shapefile.

Usage

- Activate Active and/or Passive Forest restoration processes using the switch buttons

- For each forest restoration intervention, select:

- Begin year of intervention using drop-down list
- Duration (in years) using slide button.

- Study area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window.

LUCCIA / SCENARIO / CONTROL OUTPUT

Purpose

- Allows choosing which indicator map to save as tif files on the disk.

Each scenario simulation can generate around 33 Gb of output data with more than 5000 tif files. A tif file is a raster map of Mozambique with pixels that correspond to the 800000 1 km² land units. The pixel value is the indicator value expressed as a real number. In order to limit use of disk space, the user can select which tif files are useful for a given study.

Usage

- Select which indicator maps are to be saved by checking or unchecking the box next to a

 given indicator map e.g.

LUCCIA / SIMULATION

Purpose

- Allows to:
 - Run a scenario simulation.
 - Stop the simulation before it ends.
 - Monitor the progress of the simulation.

Once the scenario building is complete, the user can start, stop, and monitor the simulation. Depending on the computer used, a simulation run for 20 years lasts about one hour and a half.

Usage

- Click on to start the current scenario simulation (the scenario name that appears on the first line of the console window)
- Click on to abort the current scenario simulation.
- Follow the simulation percentage completion on the horizontal blue line.
- Follow the progress of the simulation with the messages appearing in the console window.

LUCCIA / INDICATORS

Figure 2: Indicators window

Purpose

- Allows to display indicators of a chosen scenario at different administrative levels (posto, district, province, and country).

The graph can display one indicator of one scenario but for several units of the same administrative level over the whole simulation period. The administrative units can be chosen interactively on the map.

Usage

- Select a Scenario from the Scenario list.
- Select an Indicator of that scenario from the indicators list.
- Select an administrative level from the Zone list.
- Select administrative units by clicking on the map. Selected units appear in red.

- The graph type can also be changed using the drop-down list

Usage tip: the indicator list can be quickly filtered by typing the first characters of a word:

LUCCIA / EXTREME EVENTS

Figure 3: Extreme events window

Purpose

- Allows displaying reference household and land cover information on areas affected by extreme events.

The area affected by an extreme event is supplied in a shapefile. A number of predefined indicators are then calculated based on the baseline scenario simulation for that geographical extent and for the year of the event. Shapefiles of two previous events are supplied (Cyclone Freddy 2023, Cyclone Ana 2022), but those for future events can be supplied and the indicators will be generated.

Usage

- Select an existing or new extreme event by setting the:

- Affected area shapefile by clicking on to open file selection window.
- Year of the extreme event using drop-down list
(Reminder: If the extreme event happens in the beginning of the year e.g. February, setting the previous year would give a better picture of the status during the event.)
- After the calculation of the extreme event impact indicators has been done, you can select a geographical level using the drop-down list
 - Then every time you select a geographical area on the map and the values of the indicators are updated.
 - Note that if you want to display the values for the impact of the whole area of the extreme event, you can select 'Whole' in the drop-down list and select the geographical extent of the event on the map.

LUCCIA / PROJECT EVALUATION

Figure 4: Project evaluation window

Purpose

- Allows making a comparison between two scenarios (e.g. to compare indicators from baseline and another scenario) to assess the impact of the implanted interventions.

Usage

- Select the scenario related to a specific project that you wish to compare with the Baseline

scenario using the drop-down list

- Select an indicator of interest using

- Select a geographical level using
- Then every time you select a geographical area on the map the graph will be updated showing the evolution of that indicator for both scenarios : the Baseline and the one you have chosen.

